

Project No. 964220

Intelligent digital tools for screening of brain connectivity and dementia risk estimation in people affected by mild cognitive impairment

Deliverable 1.2

AI-Medical Device software compliance requirements map

WP 1 – Concept governance and requirements of the AI-Mind Connector and Predictor

Authors	Alejandro Sánchez-Rico (Lurtis), Tim Govers (Radboudumc), Oda Bakken, Ira Haraldsen, Vebjørn Andersson (OUS), Christoffer Hatlestad-Hall (Brainsymph), Jeanette Mueller, Andreia Cruz (accelCH)
Lead participant	Lurtis
Delivery date	14 November 2021
Dissemination level	Public
Type	Report

Version 2.3

Table of Contents

REVISION HISTORY	2
ABBREVIATIONS	2
PARTNER SHORT NAMES.....	3
1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY.....	4
2 PROCESS	4
3 MEDICAL DEVICE REGULATION	4
3.1 Qualification.....	4
3.2 Classification	5
4 ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE ACT (PROPOSAL) - CLASSIFICATION	5
5 DOCUMENTATION AND REQUIREMENTS	5
6 ANNEX I – MDR & AIA ASSESSMENT AND MANAGEMENT TOOL.....	6
7 ANNEX II – REQUIREMENTS	11
8 ANNEX III - VALID CLINICAL ASSOCIATION INITIAL ANALYSIS.....	20
9 REFERENCES.....	24

Revision History

Author(s)	Description	Date
Alejandro Sánchez-Rico (Lurtis)	Draft deliverable	30/09/2021
Oda Bakken (OUS Legal)	Revision of the AI section	08/10/2021
Tim Govers (Radboudumc)	Internal Review	18/10/2021
Alejandro Sánchez-Rico (Lurtis)	Second draft with revision integrated	19/10/2021
Jeanette Mueller (accelCH), Christoffer Hatlestad-Hall (Brainsymph), Ira Haraldsen, Vebjørn Andersson (OUS)	Deliverable restructuring	11/11/2021
Andreia Cruz, Jeanette Mueller (accelCH)	Revision	12/11/2021
Ira Haraldsen, Vebjørn Andersson, Lina Plataniti (OUS)	Final version	14/11/2021

Abbreviations

AD	Alzheimer's Disease
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AIA	Artificial Intelligence Act
APOE	Apolipoprotein E
CANTAB®	Cambridge Neuropsychological Test Automated Battery
CE	CE marking on products indicating that they have been assessed to meet high safety, health, and environmental protection requirements
EEG	Electroencephalograph
Eudamed	EU Medical Device database
DL	Deep Learning
MCI	Mild Cognitive Impairment
MDCG	Medical Device Coordination Group
MDD	Medical Device Directive
MDR	Medical Device Regulation
MDSW	Medical Device Software
ML	Machine Learning
WP	Work Package
SaMD	Software as a Medical Device
UDI	Unique Device Identification

Partner Short Names

OUS	Oslo University Hospital
accelCH	accelopment Schweiz AG
Brainsymph	BrainSymph AS
Lurtis	Lurtis Rules S.L
Radboudumc	Radboud University Medical Center

1 Executive Summary

This document refers to the preliminary assessment of the Medical Device Regulation (MDR)¹ and the Artificial Intelligence Act (AIA) proposal² in relation to AI-Mind. “AI-Mind” refers to the AI-Mind connector and predictor tools.

The MDR is a new set of regulations that governs the production and distribution of medical devices in Europe. Compliance with the MDR is mandatory for medical device companies that want to put their products in the European marketplace. The MDR represents brand new regulations with a lot of changes from the previous Medical Device Directive (MDD) and replaced the MDD as of May 2021.

The AIA is the European Commission’s proposal of harmonised rules regarding AI applications, published on 21st April 2021. The goal is to regulate the use of AI and promote it by imposing extensive documentation, training, and monitoring requirements. Any company in the EU market will be affected by the AIA. *Based on a preliminary assessment, our hypothesis is that AI-Mind will most likely be considered a class IIa medical device and a high-risk AI system.*

2 Process

We analysed the AI-Mind solution and evaluated it against the MDR and the AIA in this part of the process. Based on this analysis, the attached matrix (Annex I) has been developed, which works as an assessment tool and a management tool for all involved parties. Regarding the assessment, every condition of the MDR or the AIA that must be met was listed. We have then assessed whether or not AI-Mind actually meets these conditions. Based on the outcome (e.g. whether AI-Mind is considered a high or low-risk AI system), the required documentation and guidelines that must be in place were listed.

3 Medical device regulation

3.1 Qualification

The MDR applies to all medical devices (including software) with a medical purpose, unless listed in Article 1¹. Based on the fact that the AI-Mind solution: i) is considered a software according to the MDCG 2019-11³, ii) performs different actions on data, iii) brings high benefit to the patient, and (iv) is intended to be used for a purpose (as specified in the definition of a medical device), we conclude that AI-Mind is considered a **medical device software (MDSW)** and must comply with the MDR.

¹ Regulation (EU) 2017/745 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 April 2017 on medical devices (MDR). <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32017R0745>

² Proposal for a regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council laying down harmonised rules on artificial intelligence (artificial intelligence act) and amending certain Union legislative acts (AIA). <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52021PC0206>

³ Guidance on Qualification and Classification of Software in Regulation (EU) 2017/745 – MDR and Regulation (EU) 2017/746 – IVDR. <https://ec.europa.eu/docsroom/documents/37581>

3.2 Classification

The new MDR classifications¹ reflect the potential risk of harm that a medical device poses. There are four classes: class I (low risk), class IIa (medium risk), class IIb (medium/high risk) and class III (high risk).

Software intended to provide information to take decisions with diagnostic or therapeutic purposes is classified as **class IIa**, unless the decisions have an impact that may cause a serious deterioration of a person's state of health or surgical intervention (class IIb).

As the results of the AI-Mind will lead to further examinations and not direct treatment, there is a limited risk that the MDSW will lead to a serious deterioration of a person's state of health. In addition, AI-Mind's intention is to give medical professionals information to help diagnose and intervene by preventive therapy. *Our preliminary hypothesis is that the AI-Mind will most likely be classified as a class IIa medical device.*

4 Artificial Intelligence Act (proposal) - classification

The regulation differentiates three types of AI systems: i) unacceptable risk/prohibited practices, ii) high risk, and iii) low or minimal risk.

Prohibited AI practices are AI systems seen as a threat to security, livelihoods and human rights. Low/minimal risk AI practices are AI systems with specific transparency obligations, representing only a minimal or no risk for citizens' rights or safety. AI-Mind does not – in our opinion – fall in any of these categories. High-risk AI systems require a third-party conformity assessment, including medical devices in class IIa and above. As AI-Mind is considered a class IIa medical device and must undergo a third-party conformity assessment before being placed on the market, *our preliminary hypothesis is that AI-Mind will be considered a high-risk AI system.*

5 Documentation and requirements

Based on the above conclusions and hypotheses, we have listed several requirements considering the MDR and the AIA. However, we may have overlapping in some cases as AI-Mind is considered MDSW and AI. Both annexes are intended to work as a management tool during the whole process.

6 Annex I – MDR & AIA assessment and management tool

MEDICAL DEVICE REGULATION - general				
Qualification	The Medical Device Regulation (MDR) lays down rules concerning placing on the market, making available on the market or putting into service of medical devices for human use and accessories for such devices in the Union, cf. Article 1 ¹ .			
	Requirement	AI Mind connector	AI Mind predictor	Assessment
	Be classified as software according to the MDCG 2019-11 ³	The AI-Mind Connector is a software (platform) for processing EEG data, calculating EEG-derived features (including source-level connectivity and power spectra), and Machine/Deep Learning-based classification of synaptic dysfunction vs. normal.	The AI-Mind Predictor is a diagnostic support system that joins computerised cognitive investigation, EEG exam, demographic information, Tau protein analysis, and genetic risk assessment to establish the risk of dementia progression in Mild Cognitive Impairment (MCI) patients.	Software is defined as a set of instructions that processes input data and creates output data. AI-Mind processes different data to establish a risk of dementia, thus, AI-Mind is considered a software according to the MDCG 2019-11 ³ .
	Be an accessory for a medical device or a software driving or influencing the use of a hardware medical device according to the relevant regulations	AI-Mind Connector is an independent, software-based diagnostic support system.	AI-Mind Predictor is an independent, software-based diagnostic support system.	AI-Mind is not considered an accessory for a medical device or a software driving or influencing the use of a hardware medical device. Thus, the condition in step 3-5 must be met for the MDR to be applicable.
Perform different actions on data from storage, archival, communication or simple search	The AI-Mind Connector's purpose is to calculate a range of relevant EEG-derived features with the aim of classifying synaptic dysfunction using separate ML and DL models.	The AI-Mind Predictor's purpose is to predict the dementia risk for people with Mild Cognitive Impairment (MCI). In order to do this, the solution intend to both analyse and create medical information.	AI-Mind aims to analyse medical information with complex algorithm, thus, the condition is met.	

<p>The action needs to be for the benefit of the patient</p>	<p>Same as Predictor.</p>	<p>In establishing the risk of dementia in an early stage, AI-Mind will help potential patients. Starting medication and help early is crucial to slow down the course of the disease.</p>	<p>Discovering potential dementia early and be able to reduce the risk of a serious course of the disease, is for the benefit of the patient.</p>
<p>Be a medical device software in accordance to the definition of MDCG 2019-11</p>	<p>AI-Mind connector’s purpose is classification of synaptic dysfunction on the basis of EEG (DL) and EEG-derived features (ML).</p>	<p>AI-Mind predictor’s purpose is to predict the risk of dementia by analysing and creating medical information.</p>	<p>MDSW is software that is intended to be used, alone or in combination, for a purpose as specified in the definition of a “medical device” in the MDR. As the purpose of the AI-Mind solution is to predict the dementia risk by analysing and creating medical information, it qualifies as medical device and thus, a MDSW.</p>
<p>Conclusion: AI-Mind is considered a MDSW and must comply with the MDR.</p>			
<p>Classification</p>	<p>The MDR identifies 22 rules on how to classify a medical device. The rule resulting in the strictest classification (higher risk classification) always applies. MDSW is considered an active device (devices that require a source of energy other than the generated by the human body or gravity) and therefore several rules apply to its classification (MDR rules 9,10,11,12,13,15 and 22), but in case a software gives information to professionals, the main rule that needs to be analysed is Rule 11. As for the MDCG, “When a specialist determines the necessary cognitive therapy based on the outcome provided by the MDSW, the MDSW would be classified as class IIa per Rule 11(a).”</p>		
	<p>Requirement</p>	<p>AI Mind connector</p>	<p>AI Mind predictor</p>
<p>Main rule: Rule 11 states that software intended to provide information which is used to take decisions with diagnosis or therapeutic purposes is classified as class IIa.</p>	<p>AI-Mind aims to provide information for diagnosis/prediction of dementia risk to drive clinical management, and targets MCI patients to predict risk of developing dementia. It also gives professional information to diagnose and potentially intervene by preventive therapy.</p>	<p>AI-Mind aims to provide information for diagnosis/prediction of dementia risk to drive clinical management, and targets MCI patients to predict risk of developing dementia. It also gives professional information to diagnose and potentially intervene by preventive therapy.</p>	<p>AI-Mind analyses and provides information that is used to take decision with diagnosis or therapeutic purposes connected to risk of dementia. If a high risk of dementia is discovered, further treatment may be necessary - now or in the future.</p>

<p>Exception: If these decisions have an impact that may cause a serious deterioration of a person’s state of health or a surgical intervention, it is classified as class IIb.</p> <p>“Serious deterioration in the health” is not defined, but in MDR article 2 (58) b, several results of serious deterioration in the health are listed. These include life-threatening illness or injury, permanent impairment of a body structure or a body function, hospitalisation or prolongation of patient hospitalisation, medical or surgical intervention, and chronic disease.</p>	<p>The results of the AI-Mind connector solution will lead to further examination by specialists. The AI-Mind connector solution will not itself impose any treatment on the patient.</p>	<p>The results of the AI-Mind predictor solution will lead to further examination by specialists. The AI-Mind predictor solution will not itself impose any treatment on the patient.</p>	<p>The risk of developing dementia can be aligned with a serious situation or patient condition. Nevertheless, the risk of harm to the patient will not be as high, based on input from clinical professionals. This is because the results will lead to further examinations, and not direct treatment; the AI Mind gives a statistic evaluation, not a diagnostic evaluation. There is a limited risk that any of the results in article 2 (58) b) will happen. Therefore, the AI-Mind will most likely classify as a class IIa medical device.</p> <p>Because AI-Mind gives professional information to diagnose and potentially intervene by preventive therapy, this supports that it may be classified as class IIa, and not IIb.</p>
<p>Conclusion: AI-Mind will most likely be classified as IIa. Note that AI-Mind final medical device’s classification must be analysed at the end of the project.</p>			

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE ACT (AIA) PROPOSAL				
Classification	Classification of AI systems: the regulation differentiates three types of AI systems: i) unacceptable risk, (ii) high risk, and (iii) low or minimal risk.			
	Requirement	AI-Mind connector	AI-Mind predictor	Assessment
	Prohibited AI practices: AI systems seen as a threat to security, livelihoods and human rights are viewed as unacceptably risky and will be prohibited. This category includes AI applications that manipulate human behaviour to deprive users of their free will, or AI systems that enable social rating by states. Other examples include systems manipulating human conscience through subliminal techniques or exploiting the vulnerabilities of specific groups, such as for instance encouraging dangerous behaviour for minors.	AI-Mind connector is a diagnostic support system which, in combination with further examination by specialists, may establish the risk of dementia.	AI-Mind predictor is a diagnostic support system which, in combination with further examination by specialists, may establish the risk of dementia.	AI-Mind does not impose any of the risks of prohibited AI practices.
	High Risk AI Systems: Those safety components of regulated products or regulated products in itself that require a third-party conformity assessment (e.g. medical devices Class IIa and above) are considered “high-risk”. If the conditions in AIA article 6 are met, the AI system is considered high risk:			
a) The AI system is intended to be used as a safety component of a product, or is itself a product, covered by the Union harmonisation legislation listed in Annex II	AI-Mind connector is considered a medical device.	AI-Mind predictor is considered a medical device	AI-Mind is considered a medical advice according to the MDR, which is listed in Annex II, and is a “AI product itself”.	

<p>b) the product whose safety component is the AI system, or the AI system itself as a product, is required to undergo a third-party conformity assessment with a view to the placing on the market or putting into service of that product pursuant to the Union harmonisation legislation listed in Annex II</p>	<p>AI-Mind connector is classified as a Class IIa device, according to the MDR. The results of the AI-Mind solution will lead to further examination by specialists.</p> <p>In addition, a Notified Body must be involved in the CE marking for class IIa devices (MDR).</p>	<p>AI-Mind predictor is classified as a Class IIa device, according to the MDR. The results of the AI-Mind solution will lead to further examination by specialists.</p> <p>In addition, a Notified Body must be involved in the CE marking for class IIa devices (MDR).</p>	<p>AI-Mind is required to undergo a third-party conformity assessment before placing it on the market, according to the MDR, which is listed in Annex II.</p>
<p>Limited/minimal risk: typically, AI systems with specific transparency obligations. This system represents only minimal or no risk for citizens' rights or safety. For non-high risk systems, only limited transparency obligations are imposed. For example, when using AI systems such as chatbots, users must know that they are interacting with a machine so that they can make an informed decision whether to proceed. Another example is AI-enabled video games or spam filters.</p>			
<p>Conclusion: AI-Mind will most likely be classified as high-risk AI system.</p>			

7 Annex II – Requirements

MEDICAL DEVICE REGULATION		
Requirement	Description	AI-MIND
CE-marking	Devices shall be identifiable by having a CE marking on devices, by using a Unique Device Identification (UDI) and by their registration on the EU Medical Device database (Eudamed), shall have up-to-date technical documentation and a clinical evaluation to demonstrate their safety, performance, and benefit-risk ratio. For Class IIa devices, a Notified Body must be involved in the CE marking.	AI-Mind must cooperate with a Notified Body in the CE-marking process, as AI-Mind most likely will be classified as a Class IIa device.
Registration of devices and UDI system	Devices should be registered, including identification data, basic UDI-DI, certificate issued by a notified body, member states targeted, risk class and some additional information. For devices that are the subject of a conformity assessment, the UDI-DI shall be registered before applying to a notified body for that assessment.	AI-Mind research and development process are not affected by these requirements as the identification and traceability of devices will take place after the project. However, as a Notified Body must be involved in the CE-marking of AI-Mind, the UDI-DI shall be registered before applying to a Notified Body for the assessment.
Design and manufacture requirements	Devices with a diagnostic or measuring function should have sufficient accuracy, precision, and stability for their intended purpose. Device limits and range of use need to be indicated by the manufacturers. Manufacturers shall set out minimum requirements concerning hardware, IT networks characteristics and IT security measures, including protection against unauthorised access, necessary to run the software as intended.	AI-Mind needs to consider the state of the art in development life cycle and risk management in the design, research and development of the technology to address adequate design, code quality, security, verification and validation processes.
Requirements on the information supplied	The medical device in its documentation must: clearly state its intended use without misleading claims; include information to identify the device and manufacturer (on website or software); and state the knowledge, experience, education, and training required for the user of the device.	AI-Mind will need to clearly define the methods used for development, security, verification and validation during the design and development to support compliance with these requirements. Several of those requirements will be included in different deliverables of AI-Mind (D4.1 Software specifications & architecture design and D4.2 UI/UX Design and Validation Guidelines).

<p>Clinical evaluation</p>	<p>Medical Device Software (MDSW), such as the AI-Mind solution, as any other Medical Device to support clinical claims and benefits need to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Establish and maintain a clinical evaluation plan to generate necessary clinical evidence. - Identify relevant data related to device performance and safety and identify issues or gaps in the data. - Appraise the relevant data in its quality and contribution to the clinical evaluation. - Analyse data and relevance for conformity with general safety and performance requirements. - Document the relevant data, its assessment, and the clinical evidence. - Update clinical evaluation plan throughout its life cycle with data from Post-Market Clinical Follow Up. <p>To determine and justify the level of clinical evidence required, both the amount and quality of supporting data should be evaluated.</p>	<p>AI- Mind will need to address the amount and quality of its data considering the representation of the target groups; ethical principles of diversity, non-discrimination and fairness; and the sufficient quantity for the techniques applied.</p>
<p>Valid clinical association</p>	<p>MDSW input data and its output needs to be associated with a clinical condition, and the association needs to be demonstrated.</p>	<p>The processing of AI- Mind data sources (EEG, genetic and protein analysis data and CANTAB® tests) need a valid clinical association (Annex III) with dementia to confirm their utility for the analysis of the risk of dementia of a person.</p>
<p>Technical performance</p>	<p>Manufacturer should verify that the MDSW accurately, reliably, and precisely generates the intended output in real-world usage.</p>	<p>AI- Mind tests will need to confirm that the AI- Mind platform (or specific products) can reliably and reproducibly estimate the dementia risk in people affected by mild cognitive impairment. Additionally, the AI- Mind information must be given in an understandable manner to the health care providers.</p>
<p>Clinical performance</p>	<p>Clinical performance is about demonstration of the clinical benefit based on its intended purpose. Positive impact on individual health (outcome on diagnosis, prediction of risk or treatment response) based on testing the MDSW in the target population. Additionally, it should consider the benefit-risk ratio based on the state of the art of the intended use.</p>	<p>AI- Mind project will need to perform a prospective clinical study replicating real-world situations (in relation to target population, use conditions, operating environments, etc.). This will support clinical performance claims although further clinical investigations will need to be made by manufacturer/provider of the Medical Device to address the evidence on clinical benefit claims. AI- Mind</p>

		<p>clinical studies and its results will be published in peer-reviewed scientific journals.</p>
<p>Manufacturer requirements</p>	<p>Manufacturers shall comply with the regulation; maintain certificates and all relevant documentation for up to 10 years that need to be provided upon request; and have enough financial coverage proportionate to the device risk class, type of device and size of the enterprise. Manufacturers need to have several procedures in place: Risk management system, Quality management system proportionate to the device risk class, Post-market surveillance system, and a system for recording/reporting incidents.</p>	<p>AI- Mind needs to consider these requirements on the Exploitation Plan as those partners bringing AI- Mind solution to the market will need to have a quality management system covering all these aspects. AI- Mind partners, in case of direct exploitation of the project results, will recruit an expert on regulatory compliance during the project design and development. AI- Mind, in relation with the requirements of the post-market surveillance plan, may consider incorporating technical functionality to facilitate surveillance; communication with device users to obtain their real-world experience; reporting of incidents with the device and its relevant data; and gather clinical data to ensure the PMCF and continuous evaluation of the safety and performance.</p>
<p>Compliance standardisation considerations</p>	<p>MDR is limited to establishing essential requirements that products intended to be placed on the EU market must meet. The technical details and solutions supporting those essential requirements are laid down in harmonised European standards specifically developed by designated European standardisation organisations. Products designed and manufactured according to European HS benefit from a presumption of conformity on the legal requirements the HS covers. Conformity assessment procedures are easier, quicker, and less burdensome if provider is certified in HS. Nevertheless, the use of HS has a voluntary character. Providers can use other international or national standards or even develop its own technical solutions, provided that it can demonstrate that</p>	<p>AI-Mind exploitation partners should consider adopting Harmonised European Standards (published in the OJEU) to facilitate compliance with regulation requirements and support future conformity assessment of the AI- Mind platform.</p>

they are adequate to comply with the legal requirements.

There are several applicable standards:

Quality Management System (EN ISO 13485:2016)

Specifies requirements for a quality management system where an organisation needs to demonstrate its ability to provide medical devices and related services that consistently meet customer and applicable regulatory requirements.

Applies to organisations, regardless of their size, involved in one or more stages of the life cycle, including design and development, production, storage and distribution, installation, or servicing of a medical device and design and development or provision of associated activities.

Risk Management to Medical Devices (EN ISO 14971:2019)

Specifies terminology, principles, and a process for risk management of medical devices, including software as a medical device and in vitro diagnostic medical devices. The process described in the standard intends to assist manufacturers of medical devices in identifying the hazards associated with the medical device, estimating and evaluating the associated risks, controlling these risks, and monitoring the effectiveness of the controls.

Applicable to all phases of the life cycle of a medical device and to risks associated with it, such as risks related to biocompatibility, data and systems security, electricity, moving parts, radiation, and usability.

Software life cycle processes for Health Software (EN IEC 62304:2006/A1:2015)

Defines the development and maintenance life cycle requirements for Health Software with a set of processes, activities and tasks that establish a common framework for Health Software life cycle processes.

Health software includes medical device software (as part of a medical device or a device in itself) and software-only product with other health uses. Cover until software is integrated into the system, see also IEC 60601-1 or IEC 82304-1.

Health informatics - applications of machine learning technologies in imaging and other medical applications (ISO/TR 24291:2021)

Covers categories applications of medicine depending on various kinds of specialities, and clinical setting including repeated detection and/or diagnosis, real-time monitoring, and treatment prediction.

Clinical investigation of Medical Devices (EN ISO 14155:2020)

Addresses good clinical practice for the design, conduct, recording and reporting of clinical investigations carried out in human subjects to assess the clinical performance or effectiveness and safety of medical devices. Specifies general requirements intended to — protect the rights, safety and well-being of human subjects, — ensure the scientific conduct of the clinical investigation and the credibility of the clinical investigation results, — define the responsibilities of the sponsor and principal investigator, and — assist sponsors, investigators, ethics committees, regulatory authorities and other bodies involved in the conformity assessment of medical devices.

For Software as a Medical Device (SaMD) demonstration of the analytical validity (the SaMD's output is accurate for a given input), and where appropriate, the scientific validity (the SaMD's output is associated to the intended clinical condition/physiological state), and clinical performance (the SaMD's output yields a clinically meaningful association to the target use) of the SaMD, the requirements of this document apply as far as relevant.

Artificial Intelligence Act		
Requirement	Description	AI-MIND
High risk AI system requirements	High-risk AI systems compliance will require to have detailed Technical Documentation and pass a conformity assessment by a Notified Body, in addition to implementing several measures as listed below.	
	Technical documentation contents shall demonstrate the high-risk AI system complies with the requirements and provide all necessary information to national authorities and notified bodies	
	AI-Mind has to collect three types of data: 1. Training data 2. Testing data to maximise test probability of assigning the correct label 3. Validation data There are quality criteria regarding the training, testing and validation data sets used. There must be a certain degree of stability and quality.	AI-Mind will need organise the project in such way that these three categories of data can be documented.
	Risk Management System needs to be established, implemented, documented and maintained; shall consist of a continuous iterative process to identify and analyse risks; estimate and evaluate risks that may emerge; and adoption of suitable risk management measures.	AI-Mind will need to consider the Risk Management requirements during project execution and for future exploitation of the project results.
	Data and data governance. High-risk AI systems based on trained models will need to use datasets for training, test and validate that comply with set quality criteria.	AI-Mind will need to consider within T1.4 the data governance requirements and monitoring bias during AI-MIND project phases.
	Record keeping. AI system needs to have logging capabilities when operating that shall conform to recognised standards or common specifications. Should ensure a level of traceability appropriate to the intended purpose of the system. Shall enable the operation monitoring (specially on risk situations and AI substantial change) and facilitate post-market monitoring.	AI-Mind will need to consider the logging capability required in the data analysis process of the AI-MIND solutions in order to gather enough information for the traceability of the system performance.

	<p>Transparency and provision of information to users. AI system shall be sufficiently transparent to enable users to interpret the output and use it appropriately and shall be accompanied by instructions with clear information comprehensible to users.</p>	<p>AI- Mind will need to consider the explainability needs of the technology to support users understanding, as well as the information requirements of the system in its related manual and training.</p>
	<p>The Commission introduces the need for “human oversight”. This principle is geared towards the idea of the need to have human oversight to monitor and review the outputs of the AI system. It is of utmost importance for high risk AI systems, as shall be developed with appropriate human-machine interface tools and should be developed to allow humans to oversee the AI system during its deployment period.</p>	<p>AI- Mind use a “human-in-the-loop” approach. The output of the AI-MIND solution will support healthcare professionals in their care decisions for patients.</p>
	<p>Accuracy, robustness and cybersecurity. AI system shall achieve, based on its intended purpose enough level of accuracy, robustness and cybersecurity and perform consistently throughout its lifecycle. System shall be resilient to errors, faults and inconsistencies. Special attention to AI systems that learn that will need to address biased outputs and may require measures to maintain its resilience. System shall be resilient as regards attempts to alter its performance by unauthorised third-party exploits.</p>	<p>AI- Mind will need to evaluate the level of tool accuracy during the project period, test robustness and apply cybersecurity measures.</p>
	<p>Providers of high-risk AI systems shall establish, document and implement a quality management system to support regulation compliance. Quality management needs to consider similar aspects to the one required for MDR compliance, and additionally need to consider the following AI aspects:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Techniques, procedures, and systematic actions to be used for the design, development and quality control of the high-risk AI system. • Test and validation procedures to be carried out before, during and after development. • Data management: Procedure for data collection, analysis, labelling, storage, filtration, mining, aggregation and retention. • Systems and procedures for record keeping of all relevant documentation and information. 	<p>AI-Mind will need to consider these requirements in its exploitation plan as requirements for potential manufacturer/provider of these AI-MIND AI system.</p>

	Ensure the systems undergo the relevant conformity assessment procedure .	AI-Mind will need to make sure AI-MIND undergoes the necessary conformity assessment procedure, as with MDR.
	AI-MIND is obliged to take corrective action when the AI system is not in conformity with the AIA, duty to notify serious incidents or any malfunctions to national competent authorities, and need to cooperate with these authorities.	AI-Mind should have systems in place to ensure that these requirements are met.
Is AI-Mind a “provider”?	Most of AIA’s regulatory obligations fall on the party that places the system on the market (the “provider”), which can be a third-party provider or the company developing the AI itself. Distributors, importers, users and other third parties are subject to provider obligations if they place a high-risk AI system on the market under their name or make a substantial modification to it.	Whether AI-Mind is considered a “provider” or not depends on the plans for distribution and placing on the market.
AI ethical guidelines and frameworks	The presence of unfair biases of AI algorithms can be difficult to assess, and it is therefore important that AI systems are built with caution, and are trained on a data set which reflects the population	AI-Mind will need to consider data bias analysis to avoid discrimination.

Other associated regulations and requirements		
Requirement	Description	AI-MIND
GDPR	Personal data should be processed with lawfulness, fairness, and transparency; be collected for specified, explicit and legitimate purposes; be adequate, relevant, and limited to what is necessary; be kept in forms that permits identification of data subjects no longer than necessary for the purposes to which personal data are processed; and processed in a manner that ensures data security. Health data is a special category of personal data that shall not be processed unless an exception applies.	Healthcare providers will be the AI-Mind users; they collect and store patient health data for the analysis and will ensure patient rights within their processes. In this context the processing of data is following SoA procedures at each hospital. All applied technologies used for algorithm development are SoA technologies. AI-MIND tools will address the regulation requirements of the process in terms of data governance, patient information, explicit consent, human-machine interaction and assessment of the processor-controller relationship and allocation of roles between the healthcare provider and the AI-MIND solution manufacturer.

Cybersecurity considerations	The need for effective cybersecurity to ensure medical device functionality and safety has become more important with the increasing use of wireless, Internet, and network-connected devices. Cybersecurity incidents have rendered medical devices and hospital networks inoperable, disrupting the delivery of patient care across healthcare facilities. Such incidents may lead to patient harm through delays and/or errors in diagnoses and/or treatment interventions, etc.	AI-Mind needs to consider which cybersecurity measures to put in place to ensure the safety of the solution, especially given the fact that special categories of personal data are processed in the system.
Pre-market considerations	Manufacturer shall consider security by design to incorporate appropriate protection of confidentiality, integrity and availability of data, function, and services of a medical device along with the specified product security context (Authentication, authorisation, encryption, auditing and others)	AI-Mind needs to consider security requirements in the product design and development and might plan to incorporate security testing within validation testing procedures. Required documentation for regulatory submission should be prepared based on the security processes carried out during the project.
Post-market considerations	Manufacturers need to address several post-market considerations as vulnerabilities change over time and pre-market controls may be inadequate in the future. These considerations need to be part of the post-market surveillance system.	AI-Mind exploitation plan needs to consider the post-market security requirements to correctly assess the costs of medical device support and maintenance and include them within the product exploitation plan.
Marketing		
Notified Body	A Notified Body must be involved in the conformity assessment of medical devices in risk classes higher than class I. A Notified Body is appointed by a national authority to conduct conformity assessments, and issues a certificate if the documentation is sufficient.	DNV will probably take the role as a notified body.
Marketing authorisation	A medicinal product must be granted a valid Marketing Authorisation by the Norwegian Medicines Agency (NO: Legemiddelverket) prior to marketing in Norway.	AI-Mind will need to get a Marketing Authorisation before starting marketing the product. The requirements for a Marketing Authorisation must be taken into consideration throughout the development project, during the planning and execution of the clinical evaluation, in the conformity valuation and documentation, etc.

8 Annex III - Valid clinical association initial analysis

AI-MIND platform will use data from different sources to be able to analyse and predict the risk of dementia. Among this data main sources will be EEG, genetic and blood protein analysis data, and CANTAB® Tests. Clinical evaluation towards compliance require a valid clinical association between the data used and the clinical condition for that purpose needs to be analysed the association between the different data sources and the dementia.

EEG

EEG (electroencephalography) measures the potential at the surface of the scalp providing a direct measure of neural activity with excellent time resolution. This measure can be made due to the Apical dendrites of pyramidal cells that are oriented in parallel and can sum up linearly when enough neurons (50.000) activate synchronously. EEG can detect evoked responses, oscillatory activity and functional connectivity of the brain which enable the research of brain activity based on participants age and on specific mental disorders. There is a promising convergence of spectral analysis results of EEG rhythms in patients with AD. Compared to age-matched Nold, AD patients show widespread increase in δ and θ power density and posterior decrease in α and β power density with lowering of α power density peak (Adler et al., 2003; Jelic et al., 2000; Nishida et al., 2011; Scheeringa et al., 2012; van der Hiele et al., 2007). It is worth of interest to note that nonlinear measures of “synchronization” markers pointed to a complexity loss of cerebral dynamics in AD in the same frequency bands (Azami et al., 2017; Dauwels et al., 2010; Jelles et al., 1999; Pritchard et al., 1995; Stam, 2014; Stam et al., 2007; Woysville & Calabrese, 1994). Furthermore, the analysis of EEG phase coherence has shown differences between AD and Nold (Adler et al., 2003) and to the prediction of aMCI conversion to AD (Jelic et al., 2000). Cross-validation of EEG source solutions was successfully done with correlation study with clinical/cognitive status and other AD markers; indeed, clinical symptoms were positively correlated with abnormalities in β , α , and δ source activities (Babiloni et al., 2009; Dierks et al., 1993). Global cognitive status as revealed by MMSE score correlated negatively with δ/θ source activity and positively with α source activity (Babiloni, Del Percio, et al., 2016; Babiloni et al., 2009; Babiloni et al., 2011; Canuet et al., 2012). Similar features of EEG sources with some attenuation in amplitude as seen in AD patients were also observed in MCI subjects (Babiloni, Del Percio, et al., 2016; Canuet et al., 2012). These findings were confirmed by an independent approach based on minimum-norm depth-weighted estimation (Hsiao et al., 2013). Compared with aMCI subjects, AD patients pointed to reduced activity in precuneus, posterior cingulate, and parietal regions as well as increased activity in δ or θ sources in inferior parietal cortex, medial temporal cortex, precuneus, and posterior cingulate (Hsiao et al., 2013). Occipital, temporal, and parietal α source activities were more evident in aMCI patients with greater hippocampal volume, while they were intermediate in those with smaller hippocampal volume, and minimum in AD patients (Babiloni et al., 2009). Also, widespread α source activity was positively related to the volume of cortical gray matter in aMCI and AD subjects, while a negative correlation was found with widespread activity in δ sources (Babiloni et al., 2014; Babiloni, Lizio, et al., 2016).

Graph Theory Application and brain connectivity methods

The brain contains billions of neurons. Their synaptic connections represent an intricate array of network structures. Within this matrix of networks, nodes (neuronal assemblies) and links (connecting fibers) dynamically cooperate with time-varying aggregations (Fuentemilla et al., 2006; Jung et al., 2001; Makeig et al., 2002; Singer, 1990). Networks are continuously re-shaped throughout life via plastic modifications mainly governed by Long Term synaptic Potentiation and Depression (LTP/LTD). Such network configuration and excitabilities are continuously changing even in tens of millisecond,

according to the cyclic changes of the cortical state (“cortical uncertainty”) (Adrian & Moruzzi, 1939). Phase synchronization (or coherence), phase-locking, entrainment, cross-frequency (or power synchrony), and phase reset of EEG rhythms measure the degrees of functional and effective connectivity between different brain areas (Buzsáki & Schomburg, 2015; D’Amelio & Rossini, 2012; Rossini et al., 2019). Electromagnetic brain signals are generated by neuronal activities having millisecond time-constant and offer an extremely high time discrimination opportunity (Buzsáki & Schomburg, 2015; Uhlhaas & Singer, 2006).

Several tools for EEG analysis exploits graph theory (Miraglia et al., 2017), e.g. eLORETA (Canuet et al., 2011). LORETA (and its adaptations in sLORETA and eLORETA) is an algorithm representing a linear inverse solution for EEG signals that has no localization error to point sources under ideal (noise-free) conditions (Pascual-Marqui et al., 2002). In order to obtain connectivity values, a Lagged Linear Coherence algorithm is applied as a measure of functional connectivity (Roberto D. Pascual-Marqui, 2007; R. D. Pascual-Marqui, 2007). Moving from the scalp-recorded EEG potentials distribution, the cortical 3-D mapping of current density (source localization) is carried out via eLORETA as detailed in previous studies also providing the proof of its exact zero-error localization property (Canuet et al., 2011; R. D. Pascual-Marqui, 2007). Several recent publications from independent groups (Aoki et al., 2015; Barry et al., 2014; Canuet et al., 2011; Ikeda et al., 2015; Ramyeed et al., 2015; Vecchio, Miraglia, Bramanti, et al., 2014; Vecchio et al., 2015; Vecchio, Miraglia, Marra, et al., 2014; Vecchio, Pellicciari, et al., 2016) supported the idea of a correct source localization using eLORETA; such idea maintains true not only with high-density EEG recordings but also with the standard 20-channel EEG montage (10-20 system).

Graph theory has been widely applied to MRI tractography (Crossley et al., 2016), although it is mainly described for EEG/MEG data analysis (Miraglia et al., 2017; Stam, 2014). Core measures of graph theory can be computed at <http://www.brain-connectivity-toolbox.net> and further adapted by Matlab scripts (Miraglia et al., 2015, 2016; Vecchio et al., 2015). In such scripts, segregation refers to the degree to which network elements form separate clusters and correspond to clustering coefficient (C) (Rubinov & Sporns, 2010), while integration refers to the capacity of the network to become interconnected and exchange information (Sporns, 2013); defined by the characteristic path length (L) coefficient). For weighted network, we referred to weighted clustering coefficient \hat{C}_i : (Rubinov & Sporns, 2010).

The mean clustering coefficient is computed for all nodes of the graph and then averaged. It is a measure for the tendency of network elements to form local clusters (de Haan et al., 2012). Starting by the definition of L, the weighted characteristic path length L_w represents the shortest weighted path length between two nodes (Onnela et al., 2005; Rubinov & Sporns, 2010). Small-World (SW) parameter is defined as the ratio between normalized C and L – C_w and L_w – with respect to the frequency bands. The SW coefficient describes the balance between local connectedness and global integration of a network. SW organization is intermediate between that of random networks, the short overall path length which is associated with a low level of local clustering, and that of regular networks or lattices, and the high level of clustering which is characterized by a long path length (Vecchio, Miraglia, Bramanti, et al., 2014); in this scenario nodes are linked through relatively few intermediate steps, and most nodes maintain few direct connections.

Aging processes significantly modulate the network configuration of brain connectivity and also affect the time-varying synchronization of rhythmic oscillations in a network organization (Vecchio, Miraglia, & Maria Rossini, 2017). Graph theory functions were applied to eLORETA on cortical sources in order to evaluate the Small World parameter as a representative model of networks architecture. On the clinical ground it is of interest the study of conditions which are considered to be prodromal to dementia as in MCI. As previously said, dementias - particularly in their early stages - mainly affect synaptic transmission and therefore represent “disconnection syndromes” (Babiloni et al., 2011;

Dauwels et al., 2010; Rossini et al., 2006; Vecchio et al., 2015; Vecchio, Miraglia, Judica, et al., 2020). A statistically significant difference in the SW organization of those MCI subjects who will progress to AD (Converted MCI, particularly those who can be defined rapid—i.e. 1-2 years—converters) was recently found. An abnormal increase in graph parameters in Converted, with respect to Stable MCI (SMCI) for the α rhythm and a decrease for the δ and γ rhythms was documented (Vecchio et al., 2018). Meanwhile, the specificity/sensitivity/accuracy is not yet satisfactory for routine clinical application (de Haan et al., 2012; Miraglia et al., 2016; Vecchio et al., 2015). Moreover, significant differences between healthy elderly, MCI subjects and AD patients have been demonstrated by showing that physiological brain aging presents greater specialization (though lower values) of SW characteristics that are higher than normal in low EEG frequencies and lower in α bands (Vecchio, Miraglia, et al., 2016). Finally, converted MCI presented a graph theory pattern practically identical to the AD one (Vecchio, Miraglia, Piludu, et al., 2017). This result is in line with $\epsilon 4$ allele of the APOE gene impact on the risk of developing late-onset AD (Huang & Mucke, 2012; Vinck et al., 2013). EEG connectivity analysis, combined with neuropsychological and genetics (i.e. ApoE alleles) could be of great help in early MCI prodromal-to-AD identification as a first-line screening method (Abeles, 1991; Rossini et al., 2019), (Vecchio, Miraglia, Piludu, et al., 2017).

Several studies converge on the idea that α rhythm is a deterministic chaotic signal involved in several functions, ranging from memory formation to sensorimotor processing and integration (Schomer & Silva, 2017), (Stam, 2014). There is evidence in the healthy people showing a positive correlation between α frequency and the speed of information processing, as well as cognitive performance (Nunez et al., 2001). In the adult EEG during resting, awake conditions α rhythms are widely recordable and dominate in the posterior brain areas, while δ rhythms are poorly represented, thus reflecting a condition of likely α - δ “reciprocal inhibition” (Rossini et al., 2006). Furthermore, it is well known that the anatomical or functional disconnection of lesioned cortical areas generates spontaneous slow oscillations in the δ range in virtually all recorded neurons. In particular, the SW decrease in the δ band represents an increase of functional inhibition. The opposite holds true for the α band. A SW decrease in the γ band in the Converted MCI is in line with previous evidence (Vecchio, Miraglia, Marra, et al., 2014) showing a decrease of SW γ band in AD with respect to MCI and control subjects. The γ band (>30 Hz) mediates information transfer between cortical and hippocampal structures for memory formation (Giri et al., 2016), particularly through feed-forward mechanisms (Miraglia et al., 2020) and coherent phase-coupling between oscillations recorded simultaneously from different neuronal structures (Başar et al., 2012). Gamma rhythms are involved in a variety of cognitive functions, including visual object processing, attention and memory (Tallon-Baudry & Bertrand, 1999) and are strictly reflecting behavioral performance (accuracy and reaction time) in several memory tasks, including episodic memory, encoding and retrieval (Kaiser et al., 2008). Gamma oscillations are pivotal in synchronization of the action potentials spike phase, a mechanism which is at the base of EEG connectivity (Nikolić et al., 2013).

Functional Default Mode Network (DMN) alterations in cognitive impairment could reflect an abnormal flow of brain information processing during resting state possibly associated to a status of pre-dementia (Abeles, 1991). Recently, the possibility was investigated to automatically classify physiological vs pathological aging from cortical sources’ connectivity based on a Support Vector Machine (SVM), applied to EEG Small World using Graph theory functions and the eLORETA software program. By applying a machine-learning classifier (SVM), the ROC curve showed an AUC of 0.9 (indicating very high classification accuracy). 83% sensitivity, 100% specificity and 96% accuracy for the classification of the AD were obtained (Vecchio, Miraglia, Alù, et al., 2020).

Genetic and blood protein analysis

The APOE gene contains three major allelic variants at a single gene locus ($\epsilon 2$, $\epsilon 3$, and $\epsilon 4$), encoding for different isoforms (ApoE2, ApoE3, and ApoE4) that differ in two sites of the amino acid sequence (Corder, 1993). The APOE $\epsilon 4$ allele increases risk in familial and sporadic early-onset and late-onset AD, is the strongest genetic risk factor for AD, compared to those carrying the more common $\epsilon 3$ allele (Corder et al, 1993; Saunders et al, 1993; Farrer et al., 1997). Only 20–25% of the general population carries one or more $\epsilon 4$ alleles, where 40–65% of AD patients are $\epsilon 4$ carriers (Deane et al., 2008).

APOE genotype is also associated with AD biomarkers, with the presence of an APOE $\epsilon 4$ allele associated with greater amyloid deposition (Drzezga et al., 2009; Morris et al., 2010; Fleisher et al., 2011), a higher degree and faster rate of neurodegeneration (Moffat et al., 2000; Caroli and Frisoni, 2010), alterations in brain function and glucose metabolism (Bookheimer et al., 2000; Bondi et al., 2005; Langbaum et al., 2009), changes in cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) measures of amyloid and tau (Vemuri et al., 2010; Tosun et al., 2011), as well as more impaired cognition (Mayeux et al., 2001; Farlow et al., 2004; Caselli et al., 2011). APOE genotype is also an excellent predictor of MCI-prodromal-to-dementia condition when combined with EEG analysis for brain connectivity via graph theory method (Vecchio et al 2018, 2020; Rossini et al 2020; Miraglia et al., 2020).

Low concentrations of β -amyloid 1-42 ($A\beta_{42}$) and high levels of phosphorylated tau (P-tau) in the cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) are hallmarks of Alzheimer's disease (AD). Tau is a protein contained within the axons of nerve cells. In AD patients, microtubules can no longer sustain the transport of nutrients and other essential substances in nerve cells, which eventually leads to cell death. Plasma P-tau181 correlated with CSF p-tau181 and PET measures of $A\beta$ and tau pathologies. Plasma P-tau181 continues to increase with disease progression, distinguishing AD from other neurodegenerative diseases better than other candidate plasma biomarkers, and it predicted increases in the number of converters to AD compared to those who converted to non-AD forms of dementia.

This result is in line with the fact that the $\epsilon 4$ allele of the APO-E gene is a major genetic risk factor for pathogenesis of late-onset Alzheimer's disease.

A blood sample will be taken from participants for RT-PCR APOE allele quantification and association studies.

CANTAB® Tests⁴

CANTAB® has been shown to be highly sensitive to cognitive dysfunction in Alzheimer's disease, showing clinically meaningful outcomes associated with impaired day-to-day function (Égerházi et al., 2007). CANTAB® Alzheimer's test batteries identify baseline impairment in Alzheimer's disease with large effect sizes, our tests discriminate the cognitive profile of MCI from Alzheimer's disease and depression (Chamberlain et al. 2011 and Swainson et al., 2001) and are highly sensitive to disease progression. The batteries tie in closely with current neurobiological models of Alzheimer's disease, exhibiting sensitivity to under-activation of the hippocampus in MCI (Fowler et al., 1997). The tests also offer considerable advantage over traditional measures (ADAS-cog, MMSE) for predicting and discriminating stable from deteriorating forms of suspected dementia at an individual level (KS, Saling MM et al., 2002). Our Alzheimer's testing batteries are clinically relevant as cognitive impairments in our tests correlate with everyday function and long-term outcomes in Alzheimer's disease.

⁴ [CANTAB® Cognitive Research Software | Cambridge Cognition](#)

9 References

Main references:

[Document 52021PC0206](#): Proposal for a REGULATION OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL LAYING DOWN HARMONISED RULES ON ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE (ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE ACT) AND AMENDING CERTAIN UNION LEGISLATIVE ACTS (AIA)
The classification assessment is based on Title II, Article 5 for prohibited AI systems, and Title III, Article 6 for high-risk AI systems.

Guidance on Qualification and Classification of Software in Regulation (EU) 2017/745 – MDR and Regulation (EU) 2017/746 – IVDR. [MDCG 2019-11](#).

[Regulation \(EU\) 2017/745](#) of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 April 2017 on medical devices (MDR).

The qualification assessment is based on Article 1, and the classification assessment is based on Annex VIII, Chapter III, Section 6.3, Rule 11.

Other references:

- Abeles, M. (1991). *Corticomics: Neural Circuits of the Cerebral Cortex* (C. U. Press, Ed.).
- Adler, G., Brassen, S., & Jajcevic, A. (2003). EEG coherence in Alzheimer's dementia. *J Neural Transm (Vienna)*, 110(9), 1051-1058.
- Adrian, E. D., & Moruzzi, G. (1939). Impulses in the pyramidal tract. *J Physiol*, 97(2), 153-199.
- Aoki, Y., Ishii, R., et al (2015). Detection of EEG-resting state independent networks by eLORETA-ICA method. *Front Hum Neurosci*, 9, 31.
- Azami, H., Kinney-Lang, E., et al (2017). Multiscale dispersion entropy for the regional analysis of resting-state magnetoencephalogram complexity in Alzheimer's disease. *Conf Proc IEEE Eng Med Biol Soc*, 2017, 3182-3185.
- Babiloni, C., Del Percio, C., et al (2016). Cortical sources of resting state EEG rhythms are related to brain hypometabolism in subjects with Alzheimer's disease: an EEG-PET study. *Neurobiol Aging*, 48, 122-134.
- Babiloni, C., Del Percio, C., et al. (2014). Cortical sources of resting state electroencephalographic alpha rhythms deteriorate across time in subjects with amnesic mild cognitive impairment. *Neurobiol Aging*, 35(1), 130-142.
- Babiloni, C., Lizio, R., et al (2016). Brain neural synchronization and functional coupling in Alzheimer's disease as revealed by resting state EEG rhythms. *Int J Psychophysiol*, 103, 88-102.
- Babiloni, C., Vecchio, F., et al (2011). Resting state cortical rhythms in mild cognitive impairment and Alzheimer's disease: electroencephalographic evidence. *J Alzheimers Dis*, 26 Suppl 3, 201-214.
- Babiloni et al. (2009) Directionality of EEG synchronization in Alzheimer's disease subjects, *Neurobiology of Aging*, 30, 93-102
- Barry, R. J., De Blasio, F. M., & Borchard, J. P. (2014). Sequential processing in the equiprobable auditory Go/NoGo task: children vs. adults. *Clin Neurophysiol*, 125(10), 1995-2006.
- Başar, E., Güntekin, B., et al (2012). Brain's alpha activity is highly reduced in euthymic bipolar disorder patients. *Cogn Neurodyn*, 6(1), 11-20.
- Bondi et al. fMRI evidence of compensatory mechanisms in older adults at genetic risk for Alzheimer disease. *Neurology*. 2005 Feb 8;64(3):501-8.
- Bookheimer et al. Patterns of Brain Activation in People at Risk for Alzheimer's Disease. *N Engl J Med* 2000; 343:450-456.
- Buzsáki, G., & Schomburg, E. W. (2015). What does gamma coherence tell us about inter-regional neural communication? *Nat Neurosci*, 18(4), 484-489.
- Canuet, L., Ishii, R., et al (2011). Resting-state EEG source localization and functional connectivity in schizophrenia-like psychosis of epilepsy. *PLoS One*, 6(11), e27863.
- Canuet, L., Tellado, I., et al (2012). Resting-state network disruption and APOE genotype in Alzheimer's disease: a lagged functional connectivity study. *PLoS One*, 7(9), e46289.
- Caroli and Frisoni. The dynamics of Alzheimer's disease biomarkers in the Alzheimer's Disease Neuroimaging Initiative cohort. *Neurobiol Aging*. 2010 Aug;31(8):1263-74.
- Caselli et al. Longitudinal modeling of frontal cognition in APOE ε4 homozygotes, heterozygotes, and noncarriers. *Neurology*. 2011 Apr 19; 76(16): 1383–1388.
- Chamberlain R., Wengenack T. M., et al (2011). Magnetic resonance imaging of amyloid plaques in transgenic mouse models of Alzheimer's disease. *Curr. Med. Imaging Rev*. 7, 3–7.
- Corder EH et al. Gene dose of apolipoprotein E type 4 allele and the risk of Alzheimer's disease in late onset families. 1993

- Aug 13;261(5123):921-3.
- Crossley, N. A., Fox, P. T., & Bullmore, E. T. (2016). Meta-connectomics: human brain network and connectivity meta-analyses. *Psychol Med*, 46(5), 897-907.
- D'Amelio, M., & Rossini, P. M. (2012). Brain excitability and connectivity of neuronal assemblies in Alzheimer's disease: from animal models to human findings. *Prog Neurobiol*, 99(1), 42-60.
- Dauwels, J., Vialatte, F et al (2010). A comparative study of synchrony measures for the early diagnosis of Alzheimer's disease based on EEG. *Neuroimage*, 49(1), 668-693.
- Deane R, Sagare A, et al. apoE isoform-specific disruption of amyloid beta peptide clearance from mouse brain. *J Clin Invest* 2008;118:4002–4013.
- de Haan, W., van der Flier, W. M., et al (2012). Disruption of functional brain networks in Alzheimer's disease: what can we learn from graph spectral analysis of resting-state magnetoencephalography? *Brain Connect*, 2(2), 45-55.
- Dierks, T., Ihl, R., Frölich, L., & Maurer, K. (1993). Dementia of the Alzheimer type: effects on the spontaneous EEG described by dipole sources. *Psychiatry Res*, 50(3), 151-162.
- Drzezga et al., Effect of APOE genotype on amyloid plaque load and gray matter volume in Alzheimer disease. *Neurology*. April 28, 2009; 72 (17)
- Égerházi A, Berecz R, Bartók E, Degrell I. Automated Neuropsychological Test Battery (CANTAB®) in mild cognitive impairment and in Alzheimer's disease. *Progress in Neuro-Psychopharmacology and Biological Psychiatry*. 2007;31(3):746–751.
- Farlow MR. Impact of APOE in mild cognitive impairment. *Neurology* 2004 Nov 23;63(10):1898-901.
- Farrer LA, Cupples LA, et al. Effects of age, sex, and ethnicity on the association between apolipoprotein E genotype and Alzheimer disease. A meta-analysis. APOE and Alzheimer Disease Meta Analysis Consortium. *JAMA* 1997;278:1349–1356.
- Fleisher et al., Chronic divalproex sodium use and brain atrophy in Alzheimer disease. *Neurology*. 2011 Sep 27;77(13):1263-71.
- Fowler, K. S., Saling, M. M., Conway, E. L., et al (1997) Computerized neuropsychological tests in the early detection of dementia: prospective findings. *Journal of the International Neuropsychological Society*, 3, 139–146.
- Fuentemilla, L., Marco-Pallarés, J., & Grau, C. (2006). Modulation of spectral power and of phase resetting of EEG contributes differentially to the generation of auditory event-related potentials. *Neuroimage*, 30(3), 909-916.
- Giri, M., Zhang, M., & Lü, Y. (2016). Genes associated with Alzheimer's disease: an overview and current status. *Clin Interv Aging*, 11, 665-681.
- Hsiao, F. J., Wang, Y. J., et al (2013). Altered oscillation and synchronization of default-mode network activity in mild Alzheimer's disease compared to mild cognitive impairment: an electrophysiological study. *PLoS One*, 8(7), e68792.
- Huang, Y., & Mucke, L. (2012). Alzheimer mechanisms and therapeutic strategies. *Cell*, 148(6), 1204-1222.
- Ikeda, S., Mizuno-Matsumoto, Y., et al (2015). Emotion Regulation of Neuroticism: Emotional Information Processing Related to Psychosomatic State Evaluated by Electroencephalography and Exact Low-Resolution Brain Electromagnetic Tomography. *Neuropsychobiology*, 71(1), 34-41.
- Jelic, V., Johansson, S. E., et al (2000). Quantitative electroencephalography in mild cognitive impairment: longitudinal changes and possible prediction of Alzheimer's disease. *Neurobiol Aging*, 21(4), 533-540.
- Jelles, B., van Birgelen, J. H., et al (1999). Decrease of non-linear structure in the EEG of Alzheimer patients compared to healthy controls. *Clin Neurophysiol*, 110(7), 1159-1167.
- Jung, T. P., Makeig, S., Westerfield, M., Townsend, J., Courchesne, E., & Sejnowski, T. J. (2001). Analysis and visualization of single-trial event-related potentials. *Hum Brain Mapp*, 14(3), 166-185.
- Kaiser, J., Heidegger, T., & Lutzenberger, W. (2008). Behavioral relevance of gamma-band activity for short-term memory-based auditory decision-making. *Eur J Neurosci*, 27(12), 3322-3328.
- KS, Saling MM, Conway EL, Semple JM, Louis WJ. Paired associate performance in the early detection of DAT. *J Int Neuropsychol Soc* 2002; 8: 58–71.
- Langbaum et al. Categorical and correlational analyses of baseline fluorodeoxyglucose positron emission tomography images from the Alzheimer's Disease Neuroimaging Initiative (ADNI). *Neuroimage* 2009 May 1;45(4):1107-16.
- Makeig, S., Westerfield, M., Jung, T. P., Enghoff, S., Townsend, J., Courchesne, E., & Sejnowski, T. J. (2002). Dynamic brain sources of visual evoked responses. *Science*, 295(5555), 690-694.
- Mayeux et al. Memory performance in healthy elderly without Alzheimer's disease: effects of time and apolipoprotein-E. Volume 22, Issue 4, July–August 2001, Pages 683-689
- Miraglia, F., Vecchio, F., Bramanti, P., & Rossini, P. M. (2015). Small-worldness characteristics and its gender relation in specific hemispheric networks. *Neuroscience*, 310, 1-11.
- Miraglia, F., Vecchio, F., Bramanti, P., & Rossini, P. M. (2016). EEG characteristics in "eyes-open" versus "eyes-closed" conditions: Small-world network architecture in healthy aging and age-related brain degeneration. *Clin Neurophysiol*, 127(2), 1261-1268. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clinph.2015.07.040>
- Miraglia, F., Vecchio, F., et al (2020). Small World Index in Default Mode Network Predicts Progression from Mild Cognitive Impairment to Dementia. *Int J Neural Syst*, 30(2), 2050004.
- Miraglia, F., Vecchio, F., & Rossini, P. M. (2017). Searching for signs of aging and dementia in EEG through network analysis.

- Behav Brain Res, 317, 292-300.
- Moffat et al. Longitudinal change in hippocampal volume as a function of apolipoprotein E genotype. 2000 *Neurology* 2000; 55 (1)
- Morris et al. APOE predicts amyloid-beta but not tau Alzheimer pathology in cognitively normal aging. *Ann Neurol* 2010 Jan;67(1):122-31.
- Nikolić, D., Fries, P., & Singer, W. (2013). Gamma oscillations: precise temporal coordination without a metronome. *Trends Cogn Sci*, 17(2), 54-55.
- Nishida, K., Yoshimura, M., et al (2011). Differences in quantitative EEG between frontotemporal dementia and Alzheimer's disease as revealed by LORETA. *Clin Neurophysiol*, 122(9), 1718-1725.
- Nunez, P. L., Wingeier, B. M., & Silberstein, R. B. (2001). Spatial-temporal structures of human alpha rhythms: theory, microcurrent sources, multiscale measurements, and global binding of local networks. *Hum Brain Mapp*, 13(3), 125-164.
- Onnela, J. P., Saramäki, J., Kertész, J., & Kaski, K. (2005). Intensity and coherence of motifs in weighted complex networks. *Phys Rev E Stat Nonlin Soft Matter Phys*, 71(6 Pt 2), 065103.
- Pascual-Marqui, R. D. (2007). Discrete, 3D distributed, linear imaging methods of electric neuronal activity. Part 1: exact, zero error localization. *arXiv e-prints*. Retrieved October 01, 2007, <https://ui.adsabs.harvard.edu/#abs/2007arXiv0710.3341P>
- Pascual-Marqui, R. D. (2007). Instantaneous and lagged measurements of linear and nonlinear dependence between groups of multivariate time series: frequency decomposition. *eprint arXiv:0711.1455*, arXiv:0711.1455.
- Pascual-Marqui, R. D., Esslen, M., Kochi, K., & Lehmann, D. (2002). Functional imaging with low-resolution brain electromagnetic tomography (LORETA): a review. *Methods Find Exp Clin Pharmacol*, 24 Suppl C, 91-95.
- Pritchard, W. S., Duke, D. W., & Kriebler, K. K. (1995). Dimensional analysis of resting human EEG. II: Surrogate-data testing indicates nonlinearity but not low-dimensional chaos. *Psychophysiology*, 32(5), 486-491.
- Ramyeed, A., Komater, M., et al (2015). Aberrant Current Source-Density and Lagged Phase Synchronization of Neural Oscillations as Markers for Emerging Psychosis. *Schizophr Bull*, 41(4), 919-929.
- Rossini, P. M., Del Percio, C., et al (2006). Conversion from mild cognitive impairment to Alzheimer's disease is predicted by sources and coherence of brain electroencephalography rhythms. *Neuroscience*, 143(3), 793-803.
- Rossini, P. M., Di Iorio, R., et al (2019). Methods for analysis of brain connectivity: An IFCN-sponsored review. *Clin Neurophysiol*, 130(10), 1833-1858.
- Rossini PM, Miraglia F, et al Neurophysiological Hallmarks of Neurodegenerative Cognitive Decline: The Study of Brain Connectivity as A Biomarker of Early Dementia. *J Pers Med*. 2020 Apr 30;10(2):34.
- Rubinov, M., & Sporns, O. (2010). Complex network measures of brain connectivity: uses and interpretations. *Neuroimage*, 52(3), 1059-1069.
- Saunders et al., Apolipoprotein E epsilon 4 allele distributions in late-onset Alzheimer's disease and in other amyloid-forming diseases. *1 Sep 1993*, 342(8873):710-711.
- Scheeringa, R., Petersson, K. M., Kleinschmidt, A., Jensen, O., & Bastiaansen, M. C. (2012). EEG α power modulation of fMRI resting-state connectivity. *Brain Connect*, 2(5), 254-264.
- Schomer, D. L., & Silva, F. H. L. d. (2017). *Niedermeyer's Electroencephalography Basic Principles, Clinical Applications, and Related Fields*. Oxford University Press.
- Singer, W. (1990). The formation of cooperative cell assemblies in the visual cortex. *J Exp Biol*, 153, 177-197.
- Sporns, O. (2013). The human connectome: origins and challenges. *Neuroimage*, 80, 53-61.
- Stam, C. J. (2014). Modern network science of neurological disorders. *Nat Rev Neurosci*, 15(10), 683-695.
- Stam, C. J., Jones, B. F., Nolte, G., Breakspear, M., & Scheltens, P. (2007). Small-world networks and functional connectivity in Alzheimer's disease. *Cereb Cortex*, 17(1), 92-99.
- Swainson R, Hodges JR, Galton CJ, Semple J, Michael A, Dunn BD, et al. Early detection and differential diagnosis of Alzheimer's disease and depression with neuropsychological tasks. *Dement Geriatr Cogn Dis* 2001; 12: 265-80
- Tallon-Baudry, C., & Bertrand, O. (1999). Oscillatory gamma activity in humans and its role in object representation. *Trends Cogn Sci*, 3(4), 151-162.
- Tosun et al. Relationship Between CSF Biomarkers of Alzheimer's Disease and Rates of Regional Cortical thinning in ADNI Data. *Journal of Alzheimer's Disease*, vol. 26, no. s3, pp. 77-90, 2011.
- Uhlhaas, P. J., & Singer, W. (2006). Neural Synchrony in Brain Disorders: Relevance for Cognitive Dysfunctions and Pathophysiology. *Neuron*, 52(1), 155-168.
- van der Hiele, K., Vein, A. A., et al (2007). EEG correlates in the spectrum of cognitive decline. *Clin Neurophysiol*, 118(9), 1931-1939.
- Vecchio, F., Miraglia, F et al (2020). Classification of Alzheimer's Disease with Respect to Physiological Aging with Innovative EEG Biomarkers in a Machine Learning Implementation. *J Alzheimers Dis*.
- Vecchio, F., Miraglia, F., Bramanti, P., & Rossini, P. M. (2014). Human brain networks in physiological aging: a graph theoretical analysis of cortical connectivity from EEG data. *J Alzheimers Dis*, 41(4), 1239-1249.
- Vecchio, F., Miraglia, F., et al (2015). Cortical brain connectivity evaluated by graph theory in dementia: a correlation study

- between functional and structural data. *J Alzheimers Dis*, 45(3), 745-756.
- Vecchio, F., Miraglia, F., et al (2018). Sustainable method for Alzheimer dementia prediction in mild cognitive impairment: Electroencephalographic connectivity and graph theory combined with apolipoprotein E. *Ann Neurol*, 84(2), 302-314.
- Vecchio, F., Miraglia, F., et al (2020). Human brain networks: a graph theoretical analysis of cortical connectivity normative database from EEG data in healthy elderly subjects. *Geroscience*.
- Vecchio, F., Miraglia, F., & Maria Rossini, P. (2017). Connectome: Graph theory application in functional brain network architecture. *Clin Neurophysiol Pract*, 2, 206-213.
- Vecchio, F., Miraglia, Fet al (2014). Human brain networks in cognitive decline: a graph theoretical analysis of cortical connectivity from EEG data. *J Alzheimers Dis*, 41(1), 113-127.
- Vecchio, F., Miraglia, F., et al (2017). "Small World" architecture in brain connectivity and hippocampal volume in Alzheimer's disease: a study via graph theory from EEG data. *Brain Imaging Behav*, 11(2), 473-485.
- Vecchio, F., Miraglia, F., et al (2016). Cortical connectivity and memory performance in cognitive decline: A study via graph theory from EEG data. *Neuroscience*, 316, 143-150.
- Vecchio, F., Pellicciari, M. C., et al (2016). Effects of transcranial direct current stimulation on the functional coupling of the sensorimotor cortical network. *Neuroimage*, 140, 50-56.
- Vemuri et al. Role of structural MRI in Alzheimer's disease. *Alzheimers Res Ther*. 2010; 2(4): 23.
- Vinck, M., Womelsdorf, T., Buffalo, E. A., Desimone, R., & Fries, P. (2013). Attentional modulation of cell-class-specific gamma-band synchronization in awake monkey area v4. *Neuron*, 80(4), 1077-1089.
- Woyshville, M. J., & Calabrese, J. R. (1994). Quantification of occipital EEG changes in Alzheimer's disease utilizing a new metric: the fractal dimension. *Biol Psychiatry*, 35(6), 381-387.